

**Regional Programme for the
Sustainable Management of the
Coastal Zone of the Countries of the Indian Ocean**

A REVIEW OF THE CORAL REEF MONITORING NETWORK

In member states of the Indian Ocean Commission (IOC)

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Acronyms Used

AIDE	Association pour le Développement et l'Environnement (Comores)
AMP	Aldabra Marine Programme
ARVAM	Agence pour La Recherche et la Valorisation Marine (Reunion)
APMR	Association Parc Marin de La Réunion
AFRC	Albion Fisheries Research Center (Mauritius)
CI	Conservation International
CNDRS	Centre National de Développement et de la Recherche Scientifique (Comores)
CNRE	Centre National de Recherches sur l'Environnement (Madagascar)
CNRO	Centre National de Recherches Océanographiques (Madagascar)
COI	Commission de l'Océan Indien
CORDIO	Coastal Oceans Research and Development -Indian Ocean
COREMO	Coral Reef Monitoring database
DNE	Direction National de l'Environnement (Comores)
DIREN	Direction Régionale de l'Environnement – Réunion
GEF	Global Environment Facility
FPS	Fisheries Protection Services (Mauritius)
FRTU	Fisheries Research and Training Unit (Rodrigues)
FFEM	Fonds Français pour l'Environnement Mondial
GCRMN	Global Coral Reef Monitoring Network
GVI	Global Vision International
IOC	Indian Ocean Commission
ICRI	International Coral Reef Initiative
ICZM	Integrated Coastal Zone Management
IFRECOR	French Initiative for Coral Reefs in French Overseas Territories
IHSM	Institut Halieutique des Sciences Marines (Tulear, Madagascar)
ITMEMS II	International Tropical Marine and Managment Symposium II (Manila)
MOI	Mauritius Oceanography Institute
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MENR	Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources (Seychelles)
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
ReCoMaP	Regional Programme for the Sustainable Management of the Coastal Zone of the Countries of the Indian Ocean
RR	Reseau Recif (the Coral Reef Monitoring network in the IOC countries)
RR NFP	National Focal Point (IOC Reef Network)
RR PFN	Réseau Récife Point Focal National
SCMRT-MPA	Seychelles Centre for Marine Research & Technology - Marine Parks Authority
SFNCRN	Seychelles National Coral Reef Network
WIO	Western Indian Ocean
WIO-LaB	Western Indian Ocean Land Based sources of pollution
WWF	Worldwide Fund for Nature
WCS	Wildlife Conservation Society

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Executive Summary

In 1984, the Indian Ocean Commission (IOC) was created to assist its member countries (Mauritius, Madagascar, Comoros, Seychelles and La Reunion) in sustainable development and in particular with issues requiring a regional approach. One such issue is the regional monitoring of coral reefs under the aegis of the Global Coral Reef Monitoring Network (GCRMN) that strives to produce a global report on the status of coral reefs every 2-years. These reports are based on regional reports by the collaborating monitoring organizations. The first GCRMN (1998) included a joint regional report from the IOC countries and the countries of the East African coast, but since then the IOC countries have established their own network funded by the PRE-CIO project until 2001 and the Global Environment Facility (GEF) until 2005. Until then, the IOC network (hereafter referred to as the RR (Réseau Récif) was managed by the IOC secretariat that had contracted the Agence pour la Recherche et la Valorisation Marine (ARVAM) in La Reunion to compose, train and supervise the RR.

The RR consists of a team of divers in each country led by a National Focal Point (RR NFP). Within the RR there is an interesting mix between NGO's and government institutions. In each country the RR works under the supervision of a government institution either directly because it forms part of this institution, or under a Memorandum of Understanding with the institution. Monitoring is carried out according to a standardized method taught by ARVAM (the line-intercept method). Essentially, live coral cover is monitored once or twice per year along permanent transects marked by stakes on the reef. Fish are also counted (to a distance of 2.5metres either side of the transect lines), as are the benthic species. At a regional meeting each year between the RR NFPs and ARVAM, the data were put into a computerized data base developed by ARVAM called COREMO that converts these data into graphs and figures in a user friendly way. ARVAM compiled the regional reports to the GCRMN in 2002 and 2004.

In 2003 a mid-term evaluation of the RR was carried out. The evaluation team visited each IOC country, dived with the monitoring teams at the monitoring sites to establish whether the methodologies were comparable, interviewed a large number of stakeholders and reviewed the documentation produced. The team concluded that the RR had successfully been established and had achieved its goal of being a real coherent regional network, well connected with the outside world via correspondence, conferences, workshops and the GCRMN that has explicitly complimented the RR on its performance. Key to its success appeared to be the enthusiasm of the RR members, a simple organizational structure, a lack of a bureaucratic "straightjacket" and logistical support from the IOC. Recommendations in the mid-term review concerned mainly improvement of diver safety, supply of equipment and flow of funds to the RR NFPs to cover operating costs. In addition, the mid-term review provided suggestions about the principle concern: how to make the RR sustainable, in other words how to prevent its collapse after the closure in 2005 of the GEF project, the last project to fund the RR.

In 2007, the IOC decided to have a second consultancy concerning the RR, which is the subject of the present report. Its broad purpose is to evaluate the overall role of the RR and to articulate a demand-led future for the network. In addition the interaction between the RR and the Coral Reef Task Force established under the Nairobi Convention would be described and opportunities for further collaboration and harmonization identified.

Despite a lack of funding, the RR still exists, although it is hardly an IOC organization any more because the IOC neither funds nor manages the RR. The national teams have all continued monitoring although in those countries that relied entirely on funding from the IOC (Comoros and

Madagascar) at a reduced scale. The Coastal Oceans Research and Development - Indian Ocean (CORDIO) has provided some funding in 2006 and the Regional Marine Protected Area Project funded by the French Global Environment Fund (FFEM) has provided some funding (US\$45,225) to the RR in 2007. The most sustainably-funded monitoring programs are in Mauritius, La Reunion and Seychelles. Mauritius has its own funding for monitoring via the Albion Fisheries Research Centre (AFRC) that is funded by the government. In La Reunion monitoring is also funded by the government via the Marine Park, while in Seychelles all monitoring is now done by an NGO, Global Vision International, which also has its own sustainable source of funding. In Rodrigues, the NGO Shoals carries out the monitoring with its own funds that Shoals raises itself on a project-by-project basis.

There is now a “critical mass” of trained divers in each country and enough interest to continue the monitoring, while there is great demand for the monitoring data in particular at the international level, via the GCRMN. It does not take much to keep at least the core activities of the RR going, while discontinuing the funding would be highly de-motivating especially for countries who need it most: Madagascar, Comoros and to a lesser extent Rodrigues. The main activities to be funded would be the yearly regional workshops, the running costs for the monitoring in Rodrigues, Comoros and Madagascar, some equipment for the latter two countries, training by ARVAM in the use of the new version III of COREMO and some funding to compile the bi-annual report to the GCRMN. An annual minimum budget of some Euro 50,000 would suffice.

At the national level it is mainly the skills of the RR members that are increasingly in demand. The establishment of the RR by the IOC has had a considerable value added in that it created in each country a reservoir of marine experts that are increasingly called upon to do other tasks than the monitoring for which the RR was created. These tasks include advice in EIA matters that concern the marine environment, the creation, location and demarcation of marine parks, advice on marine resource exploitation (sea cucumbers), coastal pollution, sediment and water quality sampling, awareness raising etc. The reviewer considers the continued existence of the RR as a coherent entity because of its regional perspective and exchange of experience imperative for an organization like the IOC whose mandate it is to promote regional integration and capacity-building.

The broad objective of the ReCoMaP project, under which this consultancy is carried out, is mainly related to capacity building for Integrated Coastal Zone Management. One of the questions therefore is: “What is the relevance of reef monitoring for decision making and where has the monitoring program provided guidance for decision makers?” The answer is that the monitoring program *per se* has not been used to influence decisions because it has not been designed for this purpose. To do so, the monitoring data should be linked to scores of other data, water quality and temperature being the most important. However, the cause-effect relationship between the health of corals (except for water temperature) and water quality parameters, especially threshold levels for pollution, nutrient and sediment loading is poorly understood. This makes pin-pointing a cause of reef deterioration if and when observed in the monitoring that can subsequently be addressed by decision makers very hard. Nevertheless, this review recommends that the RR tries to link water quality and temperature data to the observed health of the reefs. Water quality and temperature data are available in most IOC countries, either because they are collected by the RR itself or because they are collected by other organizations. The on-going WIO-LaB (Land Based Sources of Marine Pollution) project envisages collecting pollution data in all IOC countries. It is therefore recommended that the RR members make an inventory of what data are collected and by whom in their respective countries, try and get access to these data and identify gaps in data collecting, in particular temperature that the RR team then collect itself.

That would most probably involve installation of data loggers that could be financed under the support for the RR.

The RR forms part of the Coral Reef Task Force (CRTF) that has been established under the Nairobi Convention, which was signed in 1985. This Convention, that was a result of the creation by UNEP of a Regional Seas Program, concerns combating pollution and the protection of biodiversity. The CRTF consists of a node in the East African countries and a node in the island states of the IOC (the RR). At present there is little cooperation and coordination between the two nodes and the RR members are generally unaware of what the CRTF is doing. The reviewer does not recommend changing the structure of the RR in such a way that it is more closely integrated with the East African node as this would result in increased costs for traveling, meetings, coordination etc. The general opinion within the RR (and this reviewer concurs) was that the chair of the CRTF in Nairobi should take the initiative to set up a reporting structure whereby data from both nodes would be exchanged while every year or 2 years a representative from one node should attend the annual meeting of the other node to exchange information and report on progress made.

There are other initiatives for reef monitoring in the region that could be integrated with the RR report. There is a yearly expedition by the Cambridge University (U.K) that has reef monitoring transects on the reef in Aldabra (Seychelles). Aldabra, being remote, uninhabited and protected, could serve as a benchmark for comparison with impacted reefs elsewhere. Under IFRECOR, the French national program for coral reefs in French overseas tropical territories, monitoring takes place in French islands in the Indian Ocean (Europa, Glorieuses, Mayotte, Tromelin, Bassas da India, Juan de Noronha). There are also other monitoring methods than the line-intersect method used by the RR that are used in the region in particular in Madagascar. The most widely used of these methods is ReefCheck. The COREMO III database that the RR will use in the future has been designed to accept data from other methods of monitoring as well. In the future the RR should try and incorporate in its reports data from sites that are monitored long term by other methods as well.

It has become clear during the present review that the RR cannot continue to function adequately if each team has to find its own funding from year to year. The reviewer strongly recommends that the RR be kept as a functioning entity in a way similar to its functioning under the GEF project. There are basically three options. These are in decreasing desirability:

1. A trust Fund or Endowment could be established that would generate the income allowing the RR to continue functioning. Considering the relatively modest amount of some Euro 50,000 needed per year to fund the core activities of the network, such a Trust Fund should be well within the possibilities of the IOC to raise especially because a number of organizations that are already involved in monitoring in the region (FFEM, WWF, CI, CORDIO, ReCoMaP) could, with others, all be asked to contribute. WWF and CI both have experience with Trust Funds and Endowments.
2. The RR could be financed by another regional project, ReCoMaP being an obvious candidate; in that case a similar set-up as during the PRE-COI and GEF projects can be maintained. Of course this does not solve the problem of sustainability of the RR, but at least the RR would continue till 2011 and buy time for the establishment a Trust Fund. This option is therefore recommended, preferably *in combination with* option 1.
3. Each monitoring team tries to find its own financing. This will not be difficult in the case of La Reunion, Seychelles and Mauritius, but more difficult in the case of Rodrigues, Madagascar and Comoros. However, for the RR to remain a regional

network, at least an annual meeting and the activities of a regional focal point (to be nominated) who maintains the network, collects the national reports and compiles the regional report will have to be financed.

Resumé

En 1984 la Commission de l'Océan Indien(COI) a été créée afin d'assister ses pays membres (Maurice, Madagascar, Comores, Seychelles et La Réunion) en matière de développement durable et en particulier les problématiques demandant une approche régionale. Une telle problématique est le suivi régional des récifs coralliens sous l'égide du Réseau Global de Suivi des Récifs Coralliens (GCRMN), qui se propose de produire un rapport global sur l'état des récifs coralliens chaque 2 ans. Ces rapports sont basés sur des rapports régionaux des organisations de monitoring collaborant. Le premier rapport GCRMN (1998) comprenait le rapport régional des pays de la COI ainsi que des pays de la côte Est-Africaine, mais par la suite les pays de la COI ont établi leur propre réseau, financé par le projet PRE-COI jusque 2001 et par le Fonds Mondial pour l'Environnement (GEF) jusque 2005. Jusque là le réseau COI (que nous appellerons par la suite RR – Réseau Récif) était géré par le Secrétariat de la COI, qui avait recruté l'Agence pour la Recherche et la Valorisation Marine (ARVAM) à La Réunion pour établir, former et superviser le RR.

Le RR comprend une équipe de plongeurs dans chaque pays coordonné par un Point Focal National (RR PFN). Dans le RR il y a un mélange intéressant entre ONG et institutions gouvernementales. Dans chaque pays le RR travaille sous la supervision d'une institution gouvernementale soit directement parce qu'il en fait partie, soit à travers un Protocole d'Accord. Le monitoring se fait selon une méthode standardisée enseignée par l'ARVAM (la méthode des transects). En résumé la corail vivant est relevé une ou deux fois par an le long des transects indiqués par des piquets sur le récif. Les poissons à une distance de 2,5 m du transect sont également relevés, tout comme le benthos (sessile ou animaux lents plus larges). Dans une réunion régionale annuelle entre les RR PFN et l'ARVAM les données étaient saisies dans une base de données développée par l'ARVAM appelée COREMO qui convertit ces données en graphes et figures facilement interprétables. L'ARVAM a aussi compilé les rapports régionaux du GCRMN en 2002 et 2004.

En 2003 une évaluation à mi-parcours du RR a été effectuée. L'équipe d'évaluateurs visitait chaque pays, plongeait avec les équipes de monitoring aux sites indiqués pour établir si les méthodologies étaient comparables, enquêtait un grand nombre de parties prenantes et passait en revue la documentation produite. L'évaluation concluait que le RR avait été bien établi et atteint son objectif de devenir une entité régionale réelle, bien connectée au monde extérieur par la correspondance, conférences, ateliers et le GCRMN qui avait félicité le RR explicitement pour ses performances. La clé de la réussite semblait être l'enthousiasme des membres du RR, une organisation simple, l'absence de rigidité bureaucratique et un bon appui logistique de la COI. Les recommandations de la revue à mi-parcours concernaient essentiellement l'amélioration de la sécurité des plongeurs, la fourniture d'équipement et le maintien d'un flux financier vers les RR PFN afin de couvrir les frais de fonctionnement. Par ailleurs la revue formulait des suggestions concernant le principal souci : comment rendre le RR durable, c'est-à-dire comment éviter son effondrement après la clôture en 2005 du projet GEF, dernière source de financement du RR ?

En 2007 la COI a décidé de mobiliser une nouvelle mission autour du RR, qui est l'objet du présent rapport. Son objectif général est d'évaluer le rôle global du RR et de formuler un avenir du réseau basé sur la demande. En plus l'interaction entre le RR et la Coral Reef Task Force établie sous la Convention de Nairobi devait être décrite et des opportunités pour davantage de collaboration et harmonisation identifiées. Nous reprenons ci-après les principales conclusions de cette mission.

En dépit du manque de financement le RR existe toujours, bien que ce ne soit pratiquement plus une organisation de la COI qui n'a ni les fonds ni les capacités pour gérer le RR. Tous les pays ont continué le monitoring bien que ceux qui étaient entièrement dépendants du financement de la COI (Comores et Madagascar) à une échelle limitée. Le programme Dégradation des Récifs Coralliens dans l'Océan Indien (CORDIO) a fourni quelques fonds en 2006, et le Projet d'Aires Protégées Marines, financé par le FFEM, en 2007. Les programmes de monitoring financièrement les plus durables sont ceux de Maurice, La Réunion et des Seychelles. Maurice a son financement propre pour le monitoring par l'Albion Fisheries Research Centre (AFRC) du gouvernement. A La Réunion le monitoring est également financé par le gouvernement à travers le Parc Marin, alors qu'aux Seychelles tout le monitoring est réalisé par une ONG, Global Vision International, qui a ses propres financements durables. A Rodrigues l'ONG Shoals effectue le monitoring avec ses fonds propres qu'elle obtient projet par projet.

Il y a maintenant une « mass critique » de plongeurs formés dans chaque pays et suffisamment d'intérêt pour continuer le monitoring, alors que par ailleurs il y a une grande demande pour les données du monitoring, en particulier au niveau international avec le GCRMN. Il suffit de peu pour maintenir au moins les activités essentielles du RR, alors que l'interruption du financement serait extrêmement démotivant, en particulier pour les pays qui en ont le plus besoin : Madagascar, Comores et dans un moindre degré Rodrigues. Les principales activités devant être financées seraient les ateliers régionaux annuels, les frais de fonctionnement du monitoring à Rodrigues, Comores et Madagascar, un peu d'équipement pour ces deux derniers pays, de la formation par l'ARVAM dans l'utilisation de la nouvelle version COREMO III et un peu de financement pour compiler le rapport bisannuel au GCRMN. Un budget annuel de 50.000 EUR serait suffisant.

Au niveau national ce sont les compétences des membres du RR qui sont de plus en plus demandées. La mise en place du RR par la COI a eu une valeur ajoutée considérable par la création dans chaque pays d'un réservoir d'experts marins à qui est de plus en plus fait appel pour d'autres tâches que le monitoring pour lequel le RR a été établi. Ces tâches comprennent des avis sur les aspects de l'environnement marin dans le cadre d'EIE, la création, localisation et démarcation de parcs marins, des conseils en matière d'exploitation de ressources marines (concombres de mer), de pollution côtière, l'échantillonnage de la qualité de sédiments et d'eau, la sensibilisation environnementale, etc. L'évaluateur considère l'existence continue du RR comme une entité cohérente à cause de sa perspective régionale et de l'échange d'expérience impératif pour une organisation comme la COI dont le mandat est de promouvoir l'intégration régionale et le renforcement des capacités.

L'objectif général du programme ProGeCo dans le cadre duquel la mission est effectuée concerne essentiellement le renforcement des capacités en Gestion Intégrée des Zones Côtières. Une des questions à poser est donc : « Quelle est la pertinence du monitoring des récifs pour la prise de décisions et où le programme de monitoring a-t-il fourni des orientations aux décideurs ? » La réponse est que le programme de monitoring *per se* n'a pas été utilisé pour influencer des décisions parce qu'il n'a pas été conçu pour cet objectif. Afin de le faire les données du monitoring devraient être rattachés à une multitude d'autres données, dont la qualité et la température de l'eau sont les plus importants. Cependant la relation de cause à effet entre la santé des coraux et les paramètres de la qualité de l'eau, en particulier les seuils pour le niveau de pollution, nutriments et charge de sédiments est mal connue. Ceci rend la détermination d'une cause de dégradation des récifs, démontrée par le monitoring, que les décideurs pourraient ensuite traiter très difficile. Néanmoins la présente évaluation recommande que le RR tente de lier les données de température et qualité de l'eau à la santé observée des récifs. Ces données sont

disponibles dans la plupart des pays de la COI, parce qu'elles sont connectées soit par le RR soit par d'autres organisations. Le projet récent WIO-LAB (Sources Terrestres de Pollution Marine) envisage de collecter des données sur la pollution marine dans tous les pays de la COI. Il est donc recommandé que les membres du RR fassent un inventaire de quelles données sont collectées dans leur pays et par qui, puissent accéder à ces données et identifient des lacunes dans la collecte de données, en particulier température de l'eau, que les membres peuvent alors collecter eux-mêmes. Ceci nécessiterait probablement des thermographes automatisés qu'un appui au RR pourrait financer.

Le RR fait partie de la Coral Reef Task Force (CRTF) qui a été établie sous la Convention de Nairobi, signée en 1985. Cette convention, résultant de la création par le PNUE d'un Programme Régional Marin (Regional Seas Program), concerne la lutte contre la pollution et la protection de la biodiversité. La CRTF comprend un noyau dans les pays est-africains et un noyau dans les pays insulaires de la COI, le RR. Actuellement il y a peu de collaboration et de coordination entre les deux noyaux, et les membres du RR sont généralement peu au courant de ce que fait la CRTF. L'évaluateur ne recommande pas de changer la structure du RR afin qu'il soit mieux intégré au noyau est-africain parce que ceci résulterait en une augmentation des coûts pour voyages, réunions, coordination, etc. L'opinion générale dans le RR (que l'évaluateur partage) est que le siège de la CRTF à Nairobi devrait prendre une initiative pour mettre en place une structure de rapport assurant que des données des deux noyaux seraient échangées, alors que chaque deux ans un représentant d'un noyau devrait assister à la réunion annuelle de l'autre noyau afin d'échanger de l'information et de rendre compte des progrès réalisés.

Il y a d'autres initiatives de monitoring des récifs dans la région qui pourraient être intégrées avec le rapport RR. Il y a une expédition annuelle de l'Université de Cambridge (R.U.) qui suit des transects sur le récif d'Aldabra (Seychelles). Loin, inhabitée et protégée, Aldabra pourrait servir de référence pour la comparaison avec des récifs sous impacts divers ailleurs. Sous IFRECOR, le Programme national français pour les récifs coralliens dans les territoires tropicaux français, du monitoring se fait sur les îles françaises dans l'Océan Indien (Europa, Glorieuses, Mayotte, Tromelin, Basza da India, Juan de Noronha). Il y a aussi d'autres méthodes de monitoring que celle des transects employée par le RR qui sont utilisées dans la région, en particulier à Madagascar. La méthode la plus répandue est Reefcheck. La base de données COREMO III que le RR utilisera à l'avenir a été conçue pour accepter également d'autres méthodes de monitoring. A l'avenir le RR devrait donc tenter d'incorporer dans ses rapports des données de sites suivis à long terme par d'autres méthodes.

La présente évaluation a démontré que le RR ne peut pas continuer de fonctionner de façon adéquate si chaque équipe doit d'année en année trouver son propre financement. L'évaluateur recommande fortement que le RR soit maintenu comme une entité opérationnelle similaire à son fonctionnement sous le financement GEF. Il y a essentiellement trois options, dans l'ordre décroissant de préférence:

1. La mise en place d'un Fonds Fiduciaire, générant le revenu permettant le fonctionnement continu du RR. Compte tenu du besoin relativement modeste de 50.000 EUR par an pour les activités essentielles du réseau, il devrait être possible pour la COI de constituer un tel fonds, en particulier parce qu'un nombre d'organisations déjà impliquées dans le monitoring dans la région (FFEM, WWF, CORDIO, ReCoMaP) pourraient être sollicitées à contribuer. WWF et CI ont de l'expérience en fonds fiduciaires;
2. Le RR pourrait être financé par un autre programme régional, avec ReCoMaP comme candidat évident. Dans ce cas un montage comme pendant le PRE-COI ou le projet GEF

pourrait être maintenu. Cela ne résout évidemment pas le problème de la durabilité du RR, mais le permettrait au moins de continuer jusque 2011 et de gagner du temps pour la mise en place d'un fonds fiduciaire. Cette option est donc recommandée, de préférence en combinaison avec l'option 1;

3. Chaque équipe de monitoring essaie de trouver ses propres financements. Pour La Réunion, Seychelles et Maurice cela ne sera pas difficile, mais cela le sera d'autant plus pour Rodrigues, Comores et Madagascar. Néanmoins, afin que le RR reste un réseau réellement *régional*, au moins une réunion annuelle et les activités d'un point focal régional (à nommer) qui maintient le réseau, collecte les rapports et compile le rapport régional, devront être financés.

1 Introduction

In 1984, the Indian Ocean Commission (IOC) was created to assist its member states in sustainable development and provide coordination between its members in matters that require a regional approach. The member countries of the IOC are Mauritius (where the secretariat of the IOC is located), Comoros, Madagascar, Seychelles and La Reunion.

The IOC has had considerable involvement in environmental projects:

- From 1995 till June 2000 the IOC implemented a regional environmental programme funded by the European Union called PRE-COI. (Programme Regional Environnemental - Commission de l' Ocean Indien). Its objective was to assist the member states in developing tools for the sustainable development and management of their coastal zones and marine resources. One of these tools was the creation in 1998 of a *Regional Coral Reef Monitoring Network*, the **Réseau Récif (RR)**
- After expiration of the PRE-COI project, new funding was obtained in 2001 by the IOC from the Global Environment Facility (GEF) administered by the World Bank to keep the RR going, ended in 2004. During this project that ended in 2004, the Network was greatly expanded and became one of the more successful regional coral reef monitoring networks of the Global Coral Reef Monitoring Network (GCRMN).
- In 2006, the IOC received funding from the E.U. for a new project called “ReCoMaP” (Regional Coastal Zone Management Program). This is a five-year program that aims to enhance sustainable management of the coastal and marine natural resources with a view to contribute to poverty alleviation among coastal populations. More specifically, ReCoMaP works with partners in the South-West Indian Ocean to support Integrated Coastal Zone Management capacity building and to support national and regional institutional arrangements that can promote integrated decision making and ultimately effective Integrated Coastal Zone Management. ReCoMaP is implemented through a Regional Coordinating Unit (RCU) that is based in Quatre Bornes, Mauritius.

Although the beneficiary countries of ReCoMaP are Comoros, Madagascar, Mauritius, Seychelles, Tanzania, Somalia, and Kenya, the RR established by the IOC concerns only Mauritius, Comoros, Madagascar, Seychelles and La Reunion. The latter island, being a part of France, cannot receive funding from the IOC or GEF and collaborates with its own funding.

Since 2005, the RR was not funded any more as a self standing project nor has it been an official component of a larger project. Monitoring has continued however with ad-hoc funding from different sources in the different countries and with the enthusiasm built up by the previous 2 projects within the monitoring teams. For 2006, individual countries have received funds for monitoring from the CORDIO program while for 2007 the COI/FFEM/WWF/CI project for Marine Parks has provided funding to each of the monitoring teams to a total of U.S. \$ 24.225, including a meeting of the Regional Focal Points. For 2008 however, no sources of funding to continue the network according to its original concept have been allocated to the network and its future is insecure.

The IOC therefore initiated the present review to evaluate the overall role of the RR and to articulate a demand-led future for the network. In addition, the review should describe the

interaction between the IOC RR and the Nairobi Convention Coral Reef Task Force and to define the opportunities for further collaboration and harmonization.

2 Description of the IOC Coral Reef Monitoring Network

The RR consists of a team of divers in each country (within an NGO, a Government body or a combination of both) that is led by a National Focal Point (a person). The monitoring team works under guidance of a supervising body (usually the ministry responsible for environment). The RR is the official node for the island states in the South Western Indian Ocean for the Global Coral Reef Monitoring Network (GCRMN), a worldwide coral reef monitoring network that issues a “status report” on coral reefs of the world every 2-years. The GCRMN requests regional reports every 2-years, so the national reports have to be consolidated into regional reports every 2-years. The last Regional Report by the RR has been produced in 2005. In 2006 there was no Global Status Report by the GCRMN as a result of the attention to the devastation by the tsunami, but in 2008 the next global report will be produced.

The East African coast comes under the East Africa node of the GCRMN. Under the PRE-COI and IOC GEF projects (from 1998 till 2005), the network has been trained and supervised by ARVAM (Agence pour la Recherche et la Valorisation Marine) in La Reunion, that worked under contract from the IOC . ARVAM has also defined equipment needs, organized workshops, convened the yearly meetings of the national focal points and compiled the Regional Reports. A main element provided by ARVAM is a computer database called COREMO of which the recently completed version III is able to accept data of different levels of detail and methodology (Manta tow, ReefCheck, fish transects and quadrats) and that converts data into figures in a user friendly way. The last regional report was compiled by ARVAM in 2005, which completed ARVAM’s involvement with the network.

An important element in the success of the network has been the organization of yearly workshops whereby the focal points presented their data, discussed their problems and determined the program for the coming year. These workshops also added greatly to the motivation of the monitoring teams, especially those in more remote areas like Comoros and Madagascar. Apart from the regional focal point workshops there have been incidental workshops and conferences attended by the focal point and some of their team members such as the biodiversity workshop in Rodrigues in 2002, WIOMSA, and WIO-laB , the Bali Coral Reef Conference, ITMEMS, etc. In general it can be said that the RR is well connected internationally and does not work in isolation. The overall conclusion during the mid-term review of the network in February/March 2003 was that the RR had been successfully established and had demonstrated a satisfactory performance. This was corroborated by the secretariat of the Global Coral Reef Monitoring Network. Compared to the situation at the mid term review however, The RR has become smaller, due to lack of funding and has reduced the number of monitoring sites (Madagascar and Comoros). Although initially there were a larger number of partners in monitoring in particular in Seychelles and Mauritius, virtually all systematic monitoring is now being carried out by only one institution or NGO in each country.

3 Description of the RR monitoring protocols

Under the auspices of the PRE/COI project, guidelines for Coral Reef monitoring in the South West Region of the Indian Ocean were produced in 1999. These describe the methodology for monitoring.

The places where monitoring will take place are first determined by dividing the reef into sectors. Sectors are stretches of reef that share common characteristics. Then a *site* is determined within a sector that is representative of that sector. In each site, *stations* are demarcated with stakes that are hammered into the substrate 60 meters apart. There are usually 2 stations per site, one on the reef flat and one on the reef slope.

The methodology adopted by the network to monitor the reef is the line-intercept method whereby a measuring tape is attached to the 2 stakes forming the *station*. The length of tape crossing a particular substrate according to specified categories such as live coral (divided into categories that vary in specificity, from descriptive to species level), dead coral, algal turf, sand, sea grass etc. is measured and recorded on an under water slate. Per station 3 stretches of 20 meters are thus monitored.

The locations of the monitoring sites were determined using three criteria that together cover the state of the reef as well as possible:

- Sites that are as yet untouched and are expected to remain untouched
- Sites that are as yet untouched but that are expected to be impacted in the near future.
- Sites that are already degraded to a greater or lesser extent.

The methodology to monitor the larger invertebrates differs between the countries. In Rodrigues, surveys of invertebrates were carried out by determining the abundance of indicator species over a stretch of 2.5 metres on each side of the measuring tape. In Madagascar the 1 x 1 meter quadrat sampling method is whereby indicator species were counted in quadrats of 1 x 1 meter. In both cases the results are a certain number of organisms per square meter, so these different methods still produce comparable data.

The fish fauna is monitored by counting fish two and a half meters along each side of the tape, giving a density per unit of surface. The fish are divided into 5 categories according to their feeding habits.

The data are put into the COREMO II database that readily accepts data from different systems of data gathering. However, the fact that every monitoring team has been trained by ARVAM to gather data the same way and process the data in the same database (COREMO) ensures that data gathering throughout the network is consistent and comparable. Neither ARVAM nor any monitoring team in the network expressed a desire to change the existing monitoring protocols and techniques. On the global level, the Global Coral Reef Monitoring Network has expressed its satisfaction with the techniques and protocols employed and with the quality of the regional reports submitted. However, COREMO II has been updated and changed so that it can more easily accept data from other monitoring techniques as ARVAM strives to promote COREMO III as *the* worldwide used data system. Additional training in the use of COREMO III in 2008 is therefore strongly recommended for the entire RR.

In Mauritius and Rodrigues concern was expressed that their computers were not compatible with COREMO II and thus the input of their data had to be done separately for the compilation of the Regional Report. Before training in COREMO III starts, ARVAM should address this problem to ensure that COREMO III is compatible with all computers used by the RR.

4 The National Teams

4.1 Mauritius

In Mauritius there are 2 monitoring teams: One in Mauritius itself and one in Rodrigues. The Mauritius team is based in the Albion Fisheries Research Center (AFRC) under the Ministry of Agro-Industry and Fisheries, while the Mauritius RR also reports to the Ministry of Environment. The long term monitoring of coral reefs is carried out at 12 sites. AFRC has a team of 12 divers who carry out the monitoring around the island including the two Marine Parks (Balaclava and Blue Bay). Monitoring is done twice yearly and started in 1995. The Mauritius team also monitors physico-chemical parameters (temperature, salinity, pH, DO, BOD, phosphate and nitrate and water quality (total coliforms, faecal coliforms, faecal streptococcus) at the same sites and the results are published in the Annual Reports of the Ministry of Agro-Industry and Fisheries. The AFRC is a well equipped centre with permanent staff, its own equipment for diving and monitoring, compressor, boat etc. It has its own funding from the Ministry for monitoring while additional funding has been received in 2006 from CORDIO and in 2007 from the COI MPA project.

4.2 Rodrigues

In Rodrigues monitoring is carried out by an NGO, Shoals Rodrigues, that carried out monitoring under the GEF project until 2005. Thereafter, monitoring was continued as part of Shoals' activities that are funded through the Darwin Initiative (U.K.) and through CORDIO in 2006 and the IOC Regional MPA project in 2007. Funding from the Darwin Initiative runs out in February 2008 however. Shoals Rodrigues has its own diving equipment, compressor, boat and laboratory equipment. Monitoring is done every 6 months since 2001 in 9 sites containing 13 stations. Apart from coral cover, benthos and fish, water quality is also monitored (nitrate, phosphate, and temperature). Each year the monitoring report is sent to the Mauritius Oceanographic Institute (MOI) and the AFRC while every 2-years the data are included in the Regional Report; Shoals has consistently produced high quality reports. Although initially Shoals worked under supervision of the Mauritius Oceanographic Institute with which it had a Memorandum of Understanding, Shoals now works independently but maintains its ties with AFRC and MOI.

4.3 Comoros

In Comoros monitoring is carried out once per year by an NGO, (AIDE, Association d'Intervention pour le Développement et l'Environnement) that has been equipped and trained completely under the PRE - COI and IOC GEF projects. It works under the aegis of the Direction Nationale de l'Environnement. Seven people are involved in the monitoring of 17 stations, 3 in Anjouan, 6 in Grande Comore, and 8 in Moheli. After termination of the IOC financing, AIDE has continued monitoring with financing from CORDIO in 2006 and from the IOC/FFEM/WWF/CI MPA project in 2007. AIDE has received diving equipment from the IOC. On Moheli, monitoring has continued in 2007. Tanks were shipped to the island to do the monitoring, from Grande Comore before the diving center virtually closed, as there is no diving equipment in Moheli nor a compressor.

4.4 Seychelles

In Seychelles the monitoring in the *Granitic Islands* is now entirely taken over by an NGO, Global Vision International GVI). This NGO has a MOU with the Government (Ministry of Environment) and supplies its data to the Seychelles Center for Marine Research and Technology (SCMRT). GVI monitors 18 sites. The way GVI works is as follows:

GVI offers assistance to developing countries by providing volunteers for certain projects mainly in the field of environment and social development. These volunteers pay for their own airfare and in addition a certain sum (for the Seychelles monitoring project over 2000 British pounds), to be able to work for a certain period of time (in the case of Seychelles 5 to 10 weeks) in the project. Before they arrive in Seychelles each volunteer is sent a package of information (including on recognition of species), concerning the particular work he/she is expected to do, that he/she is expected to learn before arrival. Upon arriving in Seychelles, rigorous training is provided (again in recognition of species, for example fish or coral species) after which the volunteer has to pass an exam. Subsequently the volunteer is taken diving on the reef and has to pass a field exam before he/she is allowed to participate in the monitoring. GVI has been established in Seychelles since 2004 and is planning to stay long term in Seychelles.

Reef monitoring in the *Coralline Outer Islands* has been carried out since 1999 under the Aldabra Marine Program that now has 11 permanent survey sites in Aldabra, 8 on the outer slope and 3 in the lagoon. The Aldabra Marine Programme (AMP) is a non profit organization committed to carrying out long term monitoring and marine research at Aldabra. The AMP is affiliated with the University of Cambridge Coastal Research Unit. It consists of a core founding group of 4 scientists. It has been funded by CORDIO in 1999 and 2001, by Total/Fina/Elf in 2002 and 2003 and a host of other funding agencies and individuals such as Shoals of Capricorn and the British Royal Society. AMP has carried out monitoring from 1999 to 2006 with the exception of 2000. Since 2002, 3 new monitoring sites have been established on 2 other islands in the Aldabra group, Assumption and Astove and on St. Pierre in the Farquhar group. The data for Aldabra have not been incorporated in the regional report as monitoring has been carried out by a different group. It is strongly recommended that these data be included in the future as Aldabra serves as a benchmark to compare trends elsewhere to because there are no direct anthropogenic influences on the reef. It is unclear whether the Aldabra monitoring program will continue in the future however as the yearly expeditions do not have a sustainable source of financing.

4.5 La Reunion

In La Reunion 7 sites (14 stations) are monitored by personnel (7 divers) from the Marine Park for coral cover, benthos fish fauna and sea grass.

4.6 Madagascar

In Madagascar monitoring is carried out in 5 sites and 12 stations by 4 divers. Monitoring continues to rely heavily upon the National Focal Point who is the driving force behind the monitoring program. The monitoring program is carried out under supervision of the Centre Nationale de Recherche sur l' Environnement (CNRE) where the focal point works. In

Madagascar, the monitoring copes with different problems from the other RR members in that the distances between the monitoring sites are huge compared to the other RR members. This causes the monitoring to be much more complicated and expensive. Due to lack of funding, the monitoring has been reduced from 8 sites with 18 stations to 3 sites with 6 stations: Nosy Tanikely and Dzamanzara in the North – East (Nosy Be), and Foulpointe in the East. In 2006 and 2007 the Madagascar monitoring has relied completely on financing by CORDIO and the IOC MPA project. However, the funds from the IOC MPA project have been allocated, but not released. The focal point has carried out the monitoring when he was on site anyway for other projects.

5 Employment of RR data to support decision making related to coral reef conservation and ICZM locally, nationally and in the WIO

This question should in fact be split into two, and touches directly upon one of the overall purposes of this consultancy which is to evaluate the role of the IOC RR. If one considers only the impact that data gathering in the monitoring transects has had on decision making, the answer is “very limited”. If one considers however the impact the RR has had in a broader sense on policy, awareness raising and marine conservation, the answer is “very considerable”.

5.1 Monitoring as a tool for decision making

At the local, national or regional level, the monitoring data have not been used to influence decisions. For the monitoring *per se* to have an impact on decision-making, the monitoring data should be linked to other data, water quality and temperature being the foremost. For instance if the monitoring had noticed a sudden die-off of coral and at the same time a deterioration of water quality that could be attributed to a discharge of waste, the monitoring team could then alert the authorities to take measures to stop the discharge. But the monitoring program has not been designed to do this. The Mid Term Report therefore, recommended that water quality data should be added to the monitoring of the biotic elements of the reef, to make the monitoring more relevant to decision making. Under the WIO-LaB project, every COI country will be equipped with water quality monitoring equipment or additional monitoring equipment where equipment to monitor certain parameters is already present. In each country increased monitoring of water quality is therefore expected to take place.

In Rodrigues and Mauritius, the monitoring teams already gather water quality and temperature data. In Seychelles, water quality and temperature is monitored by the Seychelles Fisheries Authority. Comoros did temperature measurements and in La Reunion water quality and temperature are monitored by ARVAM. The RR teams should try and get access to water quality and temperature data collected by others in case these are not collected by the RR team itself and correlate these with their monitoring results. At least water temperature data should be collected, preferably by data loggers installed at the monitoring sites by the RR teams if temperature data are not available, as a high water temperature, above the tolerance level of corals has been the overriding factor in coral bleaching. This was in particular the case in 1998, when a mass of warm water caused by the El Nino phenomenon entered the Indian Ocean and caused widespread coral mortality in particular in the Maldivian islands and Seychelles, as far as Aldabra. El Nino is a periodically recurring natural phenomenon. However, the severity of the 1998 occurrence is

thought to have been caused by the fact that global warming had added an extra temperature raise to El Nino

The tolerance level of corals for other water quality parameters however is scarcely known and it would be very difficult to draw conclusions based on fluctuations in these parameters. The only certainty pertains to nutrient loading in general: Corals are very susceptible to eutrophication.

5.2 The role of the RR on a regional and global level

The COI RR is an example of real regional cooperation in the exchange of knowledge and ideas, data gathering and processing, and presenting itself to the outside world as a coherent region. There is definitely value added by the fact that the monitoring teams have worked as a regional entity. It has connected the teams with what is going on in their field outside their island in the WIO region and globally, something that has been a major factor in their motivation. Since its inception, the RR has mainly been instrumental in raising awareness about the South-Western Indian Ocean coral reefs internationally through the GCRMN “Status Report of Coral reefs of the World” and by representing the WIO at international conferences

5.3 The role of the RR at a national level

The role the establishment of the *RR itself* has had on local decision making has been considerable. The RR has created a “critical mass” of local experts that is in high demand nationally and by donor organizations. Initially created and trained to do only reef monitoring, their field of work has now expanded considerably into doing various kinds of marine work, such as Marine Protected Area selection (Madagascar, Rodrigues, Mauritius, Seychelles) demarcation and survey, water quality sampling and monitoring, (Mauritius, Rodrigues), impact assessment, fish tagging (Rodrigues), awareness raising (Comoros, Rodrigues), bioprospecting (Madagascar) etc.

6 The needs for improved outreach and communication of RR activities

In general, there is a remarkable outreach by RR and good communication between its members. Communication with the Coral Reef Task Force under the Nairobi Convention could be improved however.

6.1 Rodrigues

The Shoals Programme has an extensive outreach program with three educators who go to primary schools, (in each of which they have an educational exhibit on the reef), works with the fishing community by discussing the need for Marine Parks and involving them in surveillance, and has established a Saturday club for teenagers on reef studies. Shoals organizes lectures and excursions on shore and on the reef where they teach snorkeling and diving. Recently, Shoals has started Reef Check training for secondary school children. Furthermore, it has produced a teacher’s pack for primary schools and a film “The Reef Beneath”. The Rodrigues Government is well aware of Shoals’ activities that are viewed as very positive for the Rodrigues community.

6.2 La Reunion

The Parc Marin de La Reunion does most of the awareness-raising about the marine environment. The monitoring sites are inside the Parc and have received newspaper and TV coverage in the local media. There is a well equipped visitor's centre in the Parc and two illustrated brochures have been produced "Le Monde Merveilleux du Recif a La Reunion" and "Reserve Naturelle Marine de La Reunion"

6.3 Comoros

AIDE does awareness-raising in collaboration with another NGO called Ulanga. Under the GEF financed monitoring project, meetings have been organized in villages and for local associations with debates, video and information on coral reefs for the youth. Lectures have been given on reefs at various schools in collaboration with the Direction de 'l'Environnement (DGE). A conference on coral reefs was organized at the Centre National de Recherche et Documentation Scientifique (CNDRS) in 2005. A documentary on coral reefs and marine biodiversity has been produced to be used by school children as part of their biology curriculum and a half yearly awareness-raising bulletin, while several articles have been published in 3 local newspapers.

In the last two years, AIDE has made a tour along the coast of Grande Comore to visit the coastal villages together with members of the Fisheries Association and a representative of the National Radio to sensitize the inhabitants to coastal degradation. On Anjouan, a workshop has been held in 2006 on marine issues with the Directions of Fisheries and Environment. Lectures have been given at first year high school level on themes like pollution, climate change and coral reef issues after which the children had to do their own research on these subjects and write an essay.

6.4 Seychelles

There are several organizations that have outreach and communication programs on the reefs, but on a broader scale than about the monitoring program only. *Nature Seychelles* has a very well equipped visitors centre with lots of information plus a news letter with articles about the reefs in Seychelles and their turtle protection and tagging program. The *Island Conservation Society* distributes information on reef protection and magement and would like to be included in the monitoring program, in particular around Aride that is a special reserve. The *Aldabra Marine Program* has a website providing information on its monitoring program. The *diving centers* all provide information about reef conservation to divers and ongoing programs.

6.5 Mauritius

In Mauritius the diving community is well aware of the monitoring program and many diving clubs would like to participate but only if the get their costs reimbursed which, at present, is not the case. Awareness-raising is done by the AFRC through "internships" for students, talks in schools and for university students and lectures in the AFRC auditorium. The annual reports that contain the monitoring data receive a wide distribution.

6.6 International

At the *international level*, the RR provides the outreach via the submission of its regional reports to the Global Coral Reef Monitoring Network to be included in the two-yearly “Status of the Coral Reefs of the World” publication. Furthermore, the RR maintains a website while RR members participate regularly in international meetings, workshops, study tours and conferences such as the WIOMSA and CORDIO meetings.

In general there is extensive outreach in each country geared to its specific needs and possibilities. It is hard to see how a more “formalized” outreach of the monitoring program per se could be achieved by the RR. If funds would be available, a (half hour) T.V. film about the monitoring program, why monitoring is important and what is happening to the reefs worldwide to be shown in each RR country would probably be the best way to provide a wider knowledge about the activities of the RR to the public at large. Such a film could be made at a reasonable cost if funding became available.

7 The national linkages between the RR and other management institutions and organizations

7.1 Rodrigues

Shoals works quite independently but has good linkages to the Fisheries Protection Service (FPS) and the Fisheries Research and Training Unit (FRTU). Shoals is alarmed by the wholesale removal of sea cucumbers from the lagoon and would like to carry out a study of the impact of the sea cucumber removal on the sediment. As such Shoals could play a major role in supporting management decisions as to the exploitation of this valuable resource. Furthermore, Shoals assists the FPS and FRTU in the creation of Marine Parks in Rodrigues and is carrying out a study to show how the spill-over effect of fish from the MPA’s would benefit the fishermen by way of tagging fish in the proposed MPA. Shoals reports to the AFRC and the MOI in Mauritius and has close ties to the University of North Wales, Bangor (UK).

7.2 Comoros

AIDE works under a Memorandum of Understanding with the Direction de l’Environnement through which it can influence management decisions. It also has direct links with the Moheli Marine Park, as one of their former members works there. There is collaboration between AIDE and the UNDP for the Moheli Marine Park, as UNDP finances a business plan for the Moheli Marine Park, for the coming 4 years.

7.3 La Reunion

ARVAM and the Marine Park work with the Direction Regionale de l' Environnement (DIREN) that makes management decisions on environmental matters including management of the marine environment. As such, both institutes influence policy and management decisions.

7.4 Madagascar

The monitoring team works under the Centre Nationale pour la Recherche Environnementale (CNRE) while the national focal point is heavily involved in the MPA program run by WWF, WCS and Conservation International, in particular the latter's Rapid Biodiversity Assessment program. Besides the focal point works in a bioprospecting project with the University of Virginia (USA).

7.5 Mauritius

The AFRC is involved with a large number of stake holders, as it determines the components to be included in the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) process where the proposed activities influence the marine environment and is consulted by the government on the adequacy of the EIA. Similarly, the AFRC controls the coastal mariculture activities of the private sector and advises the Ministry on issues concerning fisheries.

8 Ways in which volunteer/private sector monitoring networks can be further supported and their outputs incorporated into national (and regional) coral reef information systems.

Thus far, no volunteer/private sector monitoring networks have been supported by the IOC. The value of monitoring lies in the provision of long term data of consistent quality. Experience in the previous phases of the RR has shown that private sector monitoring such as through diving clubs is not sustainable, and the turnover in the teams too rapid for quality control, training and supervision by the RR. Within the RR nobody expressed a desire to involve other volunteer/private sector monitoring networks. Formal direct financial support of these organizations is therefore currently not recommended by the reviewer. The RR teams are however open to receiving data from other networks such as Reef Check data from diving clubs, but the initiative should come from the clubs themselves on a volunteer basis and not because they get their costs reimbursed. Their data should be used by the RR to give a general description on the state of the reef in other places than where their own transects are located. The first priority now should be to put the existing RR on a sustainable footing.

9 The extent to which socio-economic monitoring activities are (or could be) usefully coordinated with RR information

SOCMON is a socio-economic monitoring methodology that has been adapted for the WIO region and is be used in a CORDIO managed programme. Socio economic analysis using SOCMON elements has been used in Rodrigues by Shoals in its dealings with the fishing

communities, in Comoros by AIDE in its sensibilization of environmental issues of coastal communities in Grande Comore and in La Reunion by the Marine Park staff to explain the regulations of the park . It should be emphasized however, that the combination of socio economic analysis *with broader RR information* is discussed here, not the RR monitoring information only. As a demonstration of its usefulness in coordination with RR information, the report called “Stakeholders perceptions of Moheli Marine Park”, Lessons learned from five years of co-management, produced by Community Centred Conservation (C3) provides a good example. The report combines information from the monitoring team of the RR with socio-economic information from its socio-economic analysis to come to conclusions and provide recommendations on future management of the park in particular concerning restrictions in use of the Park and the benefits to be expected from the Park. It can therefore be concluded that this kind of information combined with information from the RR can be useful for management decisions.

10 The current institutional and management profile of the RR

At present there is no institutionalized management of the network. Each monitoring team within the network funds for itself. The fact that there is still coordination and contact between the teams is to a large extent because of the close ties and personal contacts established during the PRE-COI and GEF projects. Each team has been able to secure at least minimal funding to continue monitoring. The 2008 regional report will be compiled on a voluntary basis by Jude Bijoux (national focal point Seychelles).

In conclusion it may be said that there is no more institutional management of the RR by the COI. As Mr Selby Remie (Chair of the Seychelles National Coral Reef Network and vice chairman of the East Africa Coral Reef Task Force) put it: “The monitoring capacity is being scattered and the institutional memory is fading”. The last meeting of the national focal points, essential to the functioning of the RR has taken place in 2006 in La Reunion, financed through the MPA project by FFEM. There is therefore a serious risk that the network ceases to function if no new institutional set-up and source of funding is found.

11 The current costs of the RR and the sources of funding and bottlenecks in the supply of funds to national partners.

It is not possible to determine the current costs of the RR as the monitoring is partly done on a voluntary basis, partly by organizations that are not formally part of the network (Global Vision International) or as part of other ongoing activities. There is still a monitoring network, but the *IOC* RR has ceased to exist, because the IOC provides neither the funding nor the management for the RR. Only partial funding for the national teams through the MPA project has been provided in 2007. This funding is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 - Financial Support of the Regional Marine Protected Areas Project to the Coral Reef Monitoring Network

Country	Amount (USD)	Institution	Contacts
RODRIGUES	4,225	SHOALS RODRIGUES Pointe Monier Rodrigues Mauritius Tel : +230 8311225 Fax : +230 8310287 Web: www.shoals-rodriques.org	Director : director@shoals.intnet.mu Cc : Field Centre Manager : Ms. Sabrina Désiré admin@shoals.intnet.mu
MAURITIUS	2,000	ALBION FISHERIES RESEARCH CENTER Albion Petite Rivière, Mauritius Tel.: +230 238 4100 +230 238 4829 Fax: +230 2384184 fisheries@mail.gov.mu	A contacter : Ms. Meera Koonjul mkoonjul@mail.gov.mu
COMOROS	5,810	ASSOCIATION D'INTERVENTION POUR LE DEVELOPPEMENT ET L'ENVIRONNEMENT (AIDE) Tel : +269 33 43 49	A contacter : Mr. Saïd Ahamada ahamadas@yahoo.com
SEYCHELLES	2,200	SEYCHELLES CENTER FOR MARINE RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY – MARINE PARKS AUTHORITY (SCMRT – MPA) P.O. Box 1240 Victoria, Mahé, Seychelles Tel : +248 225114 Fax : +248 224388	Managing Director : M. Ronnie Renaud Cc : Mr. Jude Bijoux j.bijoux@scmrt-mpa.sc
MADAGASCAR	10,190	CENTRE NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE SUR L'ENVIRONNEMENT (CNRE) BP 1739 101 Antananarivo Tel/Fax : +261 20 22 264 69 dircnre@wanadoo.mg	Director : Mr. Pierre Ravelonandro Cc : Mr. Jean Maharavo maharavo@simicro.mg

All national focal points agreed that for a budget of between Euro 5000 per year covering the running costs of the core monitoring activities set up under the RR project, the monitoring itself could continue. If additional funding would become available, more sites could be added, but it should be emphasized that monitoring is done to discover *trends* so adding sites to be monitored only as a short term project has limited usefulness. Added to the running costs should be:

- The supply of equipment and spare parts to Comoros and Madagascar and spare parts to Shoals Rodrigues;
- A yearly Regional Meeting by the National Focal Points;
- Training in COREMO III by ARVAM in 2008 (could coincide with the Regional Focal Point Meeting);
- The compilation of the Regional Report for the GCMN (every 2 years). This could be done on a rotation basis by one of the National Focal Points.

Table 2 - Minimum budget to keep the network operational (Euro):

Activity/Country	Estimated Minimum Costs (Euro)
Monitoring (Madagascar)	9,500
Monitoring (Comoros)	5,000
Monitoring (Rodrigues)	5,000
Equipment, O&M etc (Mauritius)	2,500
Equipment, O&M etc (Seychelles)	2,500
Equipment O&M (Rodrigues)	2,500
Equipment O&M (Madagascar)	2,500
Equipment O&M (Comoros)	2,500
Annual Regional Workshop:	10,000
Regional coordinator (rotating)	3,000
Training (ARVAM)	5,000
TOTAL:	50,000

11.1 Bottlenecks in the supply of funds

There are persistent complaints in the supply of funds especially for the operating costs. This proved particularly limiting to the activities in Comoros and Madagascar. Transfer of funds is slow and procedures unclear and cumbersome. In Madagascar, the National focal point could not access the funds because the director of the supervising institute was abroad for instance. The same problem was noticed during the mid-term review. A solution could be that the monitoring entity (not the supervising institute) sets up a Special Account, into which the funding agency transfers a certain sum. The focal point has the right to withdraw funds for monitoring activities and sends a statement of expenses accompanied by receipts to the funding agency whenever funds in the special account reach a certain minimum level. The funding agency reviews the statement of expenses and if approved, sends a replenishment to the special account.

12 Future sources (and management) of funding for RR sites and network management

It has become clear during this review that the network cannot continue functioning adequately when each national team has to search for funding independently. Moreover, the project-to-project funding jeopardizes the continuity of the monitoring and is de-motivating. Added to this problem is the fact that there is great demand for the skills the national focal points have acquired under the project and they are now increasingly employed by other organizations. Monitoring takes only a small part of their time, but if they have to do fund raising and coordination as well that adds a burden they may not want to take up. It is also difficult for these focal points to appoint and train a successor if there is no funding available to ensure that these successors can indeed continue the work they have been trained to do.

There is great interest and experience in monitoring, not in fund raising. That should also not be the task of the focal points. Fund raising for something like a regional program should be done at a higher level, the COI being the obvious candidate. The main question therefore is how to make the RR financially sustainable. Once financial sustainability is assured, the rest will follow, as equipment, training, enthusiastic divers etc. are now available in each country or can easily be supplied. The following options (in decreasing desirability) can be considered:

12.1 Trust Fund

Ideally, a Trust Fund or endowment could be set up whose revenues ensure the sustainability of the RR. Considering the relatively limited amount of about Euro 50.000 per year needed to continue the core activities of the network, such a Trust Fund should be well within the possibilities of COI, especially because several organizations that are at present involved in monitoring (FFEM, WWF, CI, COI, CORDIO, ReCoMaP) could all be asked to contribute. The COI could contact these organizations plus the ones mentioned in Appendix 1 to solicit their views on contributing to the Fund, preferably after the COI has made a commitment for a contribution itself first to leverage funding. The Trust Fund could be established under the ReCoMaP project. This is clearly within the mandate of ReCoMaP as Result Area 1 of ReCoMaP is “*Monitoring, conservation, valorization & sustainable management of coastal and marine biodiversity & Natural resources of the South West Indian Ocean coastal zones are enhanced*”.

The RR focal points would, during their yearly meetings, agree on the division of the available funds for each country and other activities such as training. They would also agree on eligible expenditures. Each focal point could set up a Special Account in a local bank to which the COI transfers the funds allocated to that particular country. This could be done in one installment or in several. In case the COI prefers the latter, the focal point would submit a statement of expenses accompanied by receipts to the COI that, after approval, replenishes the Special Account. The focal point, eventually jointly with another member of the national RR team has the right to withdraw funds from the Special Account. It is strongly recommended to use Western Union for the transfer of funds to avoid delays

12.2 Regional Project Funding

The RR is financed by another regional project with the RR objectives in its broader mandate like the ReCoMaP project. In that case a similar successful set-up as during the PRE-COI and GEF projects can be maintained. The problem is of course sustainability again when the

ReCoMaP project finishes (in 2011), although chances are good that another project will finance the RR if it continues to function well. At least in the interim, before a trust fund has been established ReCoMaP should consider funding the RR for the coming 3 years.

12.3 Self-Financing

Each monitoring team tries to find its own financing for monitoring. This will not be difficult in the case of Mauritius, Seychelles and La Reunion, but more difficult for Rodrigues, Comoros and Madagascar. In order for the RR to remain a regional network however a regional focal point who maintains the network, collects the national reports and compiles the regional report will still have to be nominated and financed.

13 Weak points in national institutional support and recommendations for strengthening

It is of the utmost importance that the monitoring teams are firmly supported by the National Governments through agreements or Memoranda of Understanding with the supervising Government Institute (tutelle). As the IOC works at government level in each of its member states, it is important that it supports government endorsed activities that can contribute to national and regional policy.

A weak point in national institutional support of the RR is that only in Mauritius and La Reunion the RR is directly supported by the Government, in La Reunion via the Marine Park and the Direction Regionale de l' Environnement and in Mauritius via the Albion Fisheries Research Center. In all other countries plus Rodrigues, the government does not financially support the monitoring teams.

For Rodrigues, the Rodriguan government could request Mauritius to support the monitoring, as it could argue that being one country, there should be no reason why monitoring is supported by the Government in Mauritius and not in Rodrigues.

In Comoros there is concern within the Direction de l' Environnement, that only personnel from AIDE is trained and personnel of the Marine Park in Moheli. As such there is a risk that if staff from AIDE leaves, there is no continuation of the monitoring. The Director General has therefore recommended to train at least 2 government employees to guarantee continuation in case AIDE stops the monitoring. Besides, better communication of the activities by the RR to the Department of Environment has been requested.

In Madagascar the focal point works inside the supervising institute (CNRE) that allows him to carry out monitoring as part of his job description. However, a weak point is that financing goes through CRNE that has proven in 2007 not to work. It is recommended that the national focal points should have direct access to the funding allocated to their activities. Besides, it has been mentioned that the focal point works too much in isolation. A Memorandum of Understanding between the CNRE and the Ministere de la Recherche Scientifique et de l' Enseignement Superieur (MRSIS) should ensure better support and cooperation between the various government institutions such as the Centre National de Recherche Oceanographique in Nosy Be and the Institute Halieutique et Recherches Marines in Tulear.

Apart from the above arrangements, it is unrealistic to expect more support from the respective governments as far as funding of national RR activities is concerned as there are too many competing priorities especially in Comoros, Madagascar and Seychelles. The RR is also considered to be able to solicit funding elsewhere. From an institutional point of view, the RR can function adequately in case the respective Governments allow the network to function and do not put up bureaucratic hurdles, while encouraging government institutions to cooperate with the RR where necessary. This has been the case since the start of the RR and here is no reason to assume this will not continue in the future.

14 Future need and role of a Regional Focal Point

It is imperative that there is a Regional Focal Point to keep the RR functioning properly. Originally the Regional Focal Point was the institution that coordinated the RR (the IOC secretariat via ARVAM). However, the IOC does not fulfill this role any more. The main functions of the Regional Focal Point such as keeping in touch with the national focal points, keeping in touch with other regional organizations such as the Nairobi Convention Coral Reef Task Force, organizing the yearly meeting, training, etc. could be done by one of the national focal points on a rotating basis. The role of the COI would then be reduced to managing and distributing the funds. In that case the national focal points should send their requests for funding directly to the IOC. The IOC could nominate someone to review the requests against the budget allocated to the particular country and receipts from previous disbursements and transfer the funds after approval. The IOC could nominate someone to perform this task as part of his/her normal work program.

15 Recommendations of the 2003 review and diver safety and training

Rodrigues. The recommendation for the division of labor between the Rodrigues Under Water Group (RUG) and Shoals with the RUG as leading partner has not materialized. The RUG does not participate any more in the monitoring. If Shoals were to leave, the Rodriguan members of Shoals could continue the monitoring program and train others if funding would become available.

In Madagascar there is still little cooperation with the Institute Halieutique et des Sciences Marines in Tulear. The recommendation for the flow of funds to the monitoring team has not been followed, resulting in inability of the team to access the funds.

In Seychelles, the monitoring situation has changed drastically with the advent of GVI. The recommendation to work with the Seychelles Marine Ecosystem Management has not been followed, but is now irrelevant.

The recommendation to link water quality parameters to the state of the reef in the reports has not been followed. Where water quality and temperature data are available, they have not been correlated to the state of the reef. This is difficult (except in the case of extremely high temperature), but at least an effort could be made.

The problem of disappearing stakes has not been resolved despite efforts by Shoals to try and drill under water. This proved not successful and the stakes are still hammered into the substrate

everywhere. Although not ideal, this method is the best the RR has and still yields acceptable results.

The website still needs updating and upgrading. At present there is nobody in the network who takes on this task.

As to diving training and safety, Mauritius, Rodrigues, La Reunion and Seychelles have adequate diving safety and training. In Comoros and Madagascar however, additional training is needed. This was again emphasized by a near accident during a Rapid Biodiversity Assessment near Tulear (not involving the RR although this could have happened to the RR as well).

In particular the state of the equipment in Comoros is a reason for concern. The testing of tanks is long overdue, there has never been visual inspection of the inside of the tanks for corrosion, regulators leak, the inflation hoses of the Buoyancy Compensation Devices us leak or don't work , divers dive without an inflatable buoy or snorkel etc. The virtual closing of the diving center at Itsandra is a major handicap, but the arrival of a new manager/dive master is expected. Training in basic maintenance of diving equipment is imperative in Comoros as there are no service facilities, while a refresher course in diving safety is recommended as soon as the Itsandra diving centre is operational again. In that case the Itsandra centre could probably provide training as well as maintenance courses. In case the Itsandra centre does not open again and new equipment, in particular a compressor is provided, it is recommended to send a diving technician to train several people in diving safety and equipment (including compressor) and in at least visual inspection of the tanks by removing and re-attaching the valve.

It is also recommended that if new diving equipment is provided it comes with the necessary tools for maintenance and parts needed for service like a good supply of silicone grease, filters for the compressor etc.

16 Training needs of RR national focal points related to supervision of monitoring and data management

At present the national focal points, having been involved in the project for many years and having received training by ARVAM (formal as well as during the annual meetings) have not expressed a need for additional training in the supervision of monitoring and data management. They all are comfortable with the present system of data gathering and management. The Comoros focal point expressed a desire to be trained better in taxonomy of groups other than fish and corals to be able to include more detailed information on other taxa.

However, a training workshop in the use of COREMO III by ARVAM is imperative for the network. All monitoring teams would benefit from training in water quality data gathering, in particular from a similar system of temperature measuring via a standardized method. ARVAM could do this at the same time as when training in COREMO III is provided. The method chosen depends to a large extent on the equipment used (data loggers) which is dependent on the amount of funding available.

17 The practical linkages (and their value) between the RR members and other relevant networks (including the East African Node, CRTF, GCMN, IFRECOR and Reef Check)

The East African Coral Reef Task Force (CRTF) has been established under the Nairobi Convention and convened first in 2002. Members are Somalia, Kenya, Tanzania, Mozambique, S. Africa and the countries of the COI, each with a national focal point. The Regional Coordinating Unit is in Seychelles. The RR can be considered as the South Western Indian Ocean node of the CRTF. However, there is as yet no joint reporting mechanism for the CRTF to the Nairobi Convention Secretariat. This makes it difficult for the RR to collaborate with the other members of the CRTF and therefore the activities of the CRTF are virtually unknown to the RR members. A reporting mechanism could be established between the East African CRTF and the RR whereby at least the regional reports could be sent to the Chair of the CRTF in Nairobi. It would also be beneficial if a representative of the East African CRTF node could attend the RR focal point meetings and vice versa every 2 years. The CRTF has supplied the GCMN with its first regional report that included the East African states and the COI RR states in 1998, after which the RR has provided its own regional reports. Considering the fact that the RR works well, it is recommended that the present structure be maintained: two nodes in the WIO region with improved data sharing under the initiative and coordination of the CRTF chair.

The Global Coral Reef Monitoring Network is an organization that has been established under the International Coral Reef Initiative (ICRI) an initiative initially funded by the U.S. State Department. Its aim is to collect data on the state of coral reefs worldwide to be published in the "Status of Coral Reefs" report published every 2 years. The GCMN requests regional reports and RR has provided its regional reports in 2002 and 2004. In 2006 there was no Global Coral Reef Status report, the next issue being 2008. There is no funding for a regional coordinator to complete the RR regional report for 2008. Mr Jude Bijoux, (Seychelles National Coral Reef Network and employed by ReCoMaP) has volunteered to produce the 2008 regional report for the GCRMN.

IFRECOR is the national program for coral reefs in French tropical overseas territories. Focusing on coral reef protection, management and research, IFRECOR is also involved in coral reef monitoring. As such it would be relevant to the RR in particular where it concerns the reefs in Mayotte, Tromelin, Bassas da India, Juan de Nova and Glorieuses where IFRECOR has monitoring data. It would be interesting for the RR to establish contact with IFRECOR to explore the possibilities for including the data for these 2 islands in the regional report.

REEF CHECK is a global environmental group established to facilitate community education, monitoring and management of coral reefs. Reef Check is active in more than 70 coral reef countries where it seeks to: educate the public about the coral reef crisis and how to prevent it; create a global network of volunteer teams which regularly monitor and report on reef health under the supervision of scientists; scientifically investigate coral reefs. Under the ICRI framework, Reef Check is a primary GCRMN partner and coordinates GCRMN training programs in ecological and socio-economic monitoring throughout the world. RR members have been trained in Reef Check techniques in Tulear, Madagascar. However, the Reef Check methodology is less precise than the methodology applied by the RR and therefore not adopted. It is a methodology more suitable for non-professionals like diving clubs. However, the COREMO III database can readily accommodate Reef Check data in case the RR were to include other groups that use Reef Check as their monitoring method. The RR should therefore be open to

offers from Reef Check monitoring organizations to include their data, in particular where it concerns a general description of the reef.

18 Opportunities and demand for increased integration between the RR and other networks (especially the East Africa node and ReefCheck)

At present, the primary network into which the RR is integrated is the GCMN. This partnership has worked well in the past and is expected to continue to do so in the future. During this review, there appeared to be no demand within the RR for closer collaboration with the East Africa node, because the members of the RR did not see how they could benefit from increased integration with this node. There was universal willingness however to share data and reports with the node once a common reporting and dissemination system has been established by the CRTF. The RR expressed the desire however to remain independent and in particular to keep their relationship with the GCMN as it is. But it was felt that the demand, structure, rationale and initiative for closer collaboration should come from the CRTF.

As to ReefCheck the RR agreed that adding ReefCheck data would be valuable if supplied on a sustainable basis and put into COREMO III. But it was felt by the RR partners, that they are at present incapable of organizing and managing more than their own monitoring programs, especially given the very limited funding available to them.

19 Benefits derived from increased participation in the CRTF by the RR members and means by which that could be achieved

The benefits derived from increased participation in the CRTF by RR members would mainly be in the exchange of experiences and ideas. However, the RR members already meet every year and are regularly attending conferences, workshops, symposia etc. where they meet other members of the CRTF such as the WIOMSA meeting in Durban in October 2007. Furthermore, monitoring is only a part time job for RR members and all work in a larger structure with multiple partners such as universities (Shoals), conservation organizations such as WWF, CI, WCS (Madagascar), Research Institutions and NGO's (Seychelles), social scientists such as C3 (Comoros) or have in-house capacity in a large variety of fields (the Albion Fisheries Research Center, Mauritius). Members of the latter institute attended for instance 38 mostly international meetings, workshops, seminars and conferences in 2005 alone. In fact it was difficult to plan this mission so that the consultant could meet with every RR focal point, as they were traveling so frequently. None of the RR members therefore expressed a desire for a more formal integration in the CRTF, as this would inevitably mean more travel, work and above all funding that could better be used for field work. It was felt that exchange of reports and eventual attending of the biannual RR focal point meeting for the regional report by a member of the East African CRTF node would be sufficient.

20 Conclusion

Long-term monitoring is the only way to detect trends. If the RR were to discontinue its activities, its efforts over the last 10 years would be largely in vain. Moreover, the Western Indian Ocean would become a gap in the Global Coral Reef Status Report.

The establishment of the Réseau Recif by the COI has resulted in the formation and training of a regional node of internationally well connected marine field experts who have expanded their expertise and interest well beyond the initial limited scope of monitoring transects and are now called upon to advise on a range of subjects. It can therefore be stated that there is a large value added to the creation of the RR.

21 Recommendations

- In view of the successful establishment and functioning of the RR, the importance of long term monitoring, the relatively low costs to keep the RR functioning and the increased attention paid to the marine environment by the donor community and the world at large, the reviewer strongly recommends to continue supporting the RR;
- To finance this support, a Trust Fund could be established. In case this proves impossible or not practicable, ReCoMaP should finance the RR until the Trust Fund would start yielding revenues;
- The IOC should provide logistical support the RR. This can be limited to the supply of funds to the National Focal Points;
- The National Focal Points should have access to a special account into which funds from the IOC are transferred;
- A regional Focal Point should be nominated among the National Focal Points each year on a rotational basis to manage the activities of the RR for that particular year;
- A yearly meeting of the RR should be held during which technical and financial matters are agreed upon within the RR;
- Training early in 2008 of the RR by ARVAM in the use of COREMO III is strongly recommended;
- ARVAM should be asked to address computer compatibility problems before providing COREMO III training;
- Every 2 years someone from the RR should attend a CRTF meeting or vice versa;
- Regional Reports by the RR should be sent to the CRTF;
- The Comoros and Madagascar should receive additional equipment and training in diving safety and maintenance of equipment. In Madagascar form a local diving center, in Comoros by a diving technician from abroad if the Itsandra center can not provide this;
- Water quality and temperature data (whether measured by the RR itself or another organization in the country) should be correlated with the monitoring findings;
- At least temperature should be monitored by the RR if such data are not available from other sources. This may require installing data loggers by the RR;

- The website of the RR should be updated and a T.V. film produced about the activities of the RR to improve outreach;
- Available monitoring data from Aldabra and a summary of monitoring data of the French islands monitored under IFRECOR should be incorporated in the Regional Reports.

Appendix 1: Potential sources of funding for coral-reef monitoring

CI - CONSERVATION INTERNATIONAL

CI is a global, field-based environmental organisation that promotes the protection of biological diversity. Working in more than 30 countries over 4 continents, CI applies innovations in science, economics, policy and community participation to protect the Earth's richest regions of plant and animal diversity. The Marine Rapid Assessment Program (RAP) of the Center for Applied Biodiversity Science at CI organises scientific expeditions to document marine biodiversity as well as freshwater and terrestrial biodiversity hotspots, and tropical wilderness areas. Their conservation status and diversity are recorded using indicator groups (molluscs, corals and fish), and the results are combined with social, environmental and other ecosystem information to produce recommendations for protective measures to local communities and decision-makers. The main focus of Marine RAP surveys has been the 'coral triangle' in Southeast Asia, which contains the richest coastal and marine biodiversity in the world. Contact: Sheila McKenna, Conservation International, 1919 Main St.NW, Washington, DC 20036 USA; www.biodiversityscience.org and www.conservation.org, s.mckenna@conservation.org

CORDIO – COASTAL OCEANS RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT - INDIAN OCEAN

This is a regional, multi-disciplinary program developed to investigate the ecological and socio-economic consequences of the mass coral bleaching in 1998 and subsequent egradation of coral reefs in the Central and Western Indian Ocean. CORDIO is an operational unit within ICRI, with objectives to determine the: biophysical impacts of the bleaching and mortality of corals and long-term prospects for recovery; socio-economic impacts of the coral mortality and options for mitigating these through management and development of alternative livelihoods for peoples dependent on coral reefs; and prospects for restoration and rehabilitation of reefs to accelerate their ecological and economic recovery. CORDIO assists and coordinates with the GCRMN in the Indian Ocean with monitoring and running the Node in East Africa, the Indian Ocean Islands and South Asia. The participating countries are: Kenya, Tanzania, Mozambique, Madagascar, Seychelles, India, Maldives, Sri Lanka, Reunion, Comores, Mauritius and Chagos. Program co-ordination contacts: Olof Lindén, World Maritime University, Malmö, Sweden, olof.linden@cordio.org; David Souter, University of Kalmar david.souter@cordio.org; East Africa: David Obura, CORDIO East Africa, P.O. Box 10135, Bamburi, Kenya, dobura@africaonline.co.ke; Island States: Rolph Payet, Ministry of Environment, Seychelles, ps@env.gov.sc

JAPAN - MINISTRY OF THE ENVIRONMENT

The Ministry of the Environment is responsible for environmental policies ranging from waste management to nature conservation in Japan. The Nature Conservation Bureau of the Ministry is responsible for conservation of natural environments including coral reefs and related ecosystems. The Bureau has conducted a national survey of Japanese coral reefs and produced coral distribution maps. In addition, the Bureau has initiated coral reef rehabilitation projects

since 2002. The International Coral Reef Research and Monitoring Center, established on Ishigaki Island, is the East Asia Seas Regional node of GCRMN to promote international and domestic coral reef monitoring. Contact: Biodiversity Planning Division, Nature Conservation Bureau, Ministry of the Environment, 1-2-2 asumigaseki, Chiyoda-ku, Tokyo 100-8975, Japan; coral@env.go.jp; www.env.go.jp/ and www.coremoc.go.jp/

NORWAY - MINISTRIES OF FOREIGN AFFAIRS AND ENVIRONMENT

The Royal Ministry of Foreign Affairs, established in 1905, is responsible for Norway's Strategy for Environment in Development Cooperation, which promotes the integration of environmental considerations in multilateral programs through multilateral/bilateral support and co-financing. The main objective of Norway's environmental assistance is the sound management of the global environment and biological diversity. Norway supports the UNEP 'African Process on development and protection of the marine and coastal environment in Africa' and bilaterally supports activities in the Gulf of Guinea, Mozambique, Tanzania, Angola, Namibia, South Africa, Sri Lanka, Vietnam, Indonesia, and China, which include coastal zone management and the establishment of MPAs. Contact: Norwegian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, PO box 8114 Dep., N-0032 Oslo, Norway; post@mfa.no; www.mfa.no

The Royal Ministry of the Environment, established in 1972, has responsibility for the Norwegian biodiversity policy and action plan; the action plan includes cross-sectoral responsibilities and coordination within the Government. The national target is to halt the loss of biodiversity, Sponsoring Organisations, Coral Reef Programs & Monitoring Networks by 2010. Basic elements of Government marine policy are sustainable management of the marine resources and implementation of an ecosystem approach. Protection of coral reefs is especially important both nationally and internationally due the vulnerability of coral reefs and their ecological and socio-economic importance. Norway has protected 6 cold-water coral reefs in national waters since 1999 and started preparation of a national network of MPAs, which will include coral reefs. Norway joined ICRI in 2004. Contact: Norwegian Ministry of the Environment, P.B. 8013 Dep., 0030 Oslo, Norway, postmottak@md.dep.no; www.odin.dep

PACKARD FOUNDATION

The David and Lucile Packard Foundation is a private Foundation based in California. It established the Western Pacific Coastal Marine Conservation Program in 1998 with the goals of long-term conservation and responsible stewardship of critical coastal marine habitats and resources, especially coral reefs and seagrasses in 7 countries in the Western Pacific: Palau; Federated States of Micronesia; Philippines; Papua New Guinea; Solomon Islands; Fiji; and eastern Indonesia. The program's funding strategy focuses on: improving individual technical skills for effective conservation and resource management; supporting networks of marine protected areas; and developing a range of targeted, applied research and analysis initiatives to provide useful information for practitioners, policy-makers, and local community members. Contact: www.packard.org

SIDA & SAREC – SWEDEN

The Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency (Sida), and its Department for Research Cooperation (SAREC) assist developing countries alleviate poverty and achieve sustainable development. Environmental aspects are integrated in all development cooperation programs to ensure compliance with Agenda 21 and other environmental conventions. The

Marine Science Program has actively promoted research cooperation and capacity building for Integrated Coastal Zone Management in eastern Africa, the western Indian Ocean and southeast Asia. National support for marine science is given to Vietnam, Sri Lanka, Mozambique and Tanzania. Many coastal projects and regional workshops are supported through the Marine Science for Management Program (MASMA), coordinated by the Western Indian Ocean Marine Science Association (WIOMSA) (www.wiomsa.org). MASMA allocates grants to researchers at national institutes on the western side of the Indian Ocean. The program's long-term objective is to improve the use of marine and coastal resources to combat poverty and environmental degradation. Sida is also the main supporter of the program Coral Degradation in the Indian Ocean (CORDIO). Contact: Håkan Berg, Sida – SAREC, SE-105 25 Stockholm; hakan.berg@sida.se

TOTAL CORPORATE FOUNDATION

This marine biodiversity Foundation was established in 1992 following requests from Total employees for a visible commitment to the environment. The main focus is the preservation of marine and coastal species, specifically: *Biodiversity*, which recognises that human progress has occurred in parallel with damage to marine species, including some extinctions. Thus a conservation partnership was developed in 1992 with the Port-Cros National Park and the National Botanical Conservatory of Porquerolles; *The Sea*, as Total extracts significant energy resources from the sea and transports these by sea, a natural interest is the preservation of sensitive marine areas. Total's aim is to implement best practice during its marine industrial activities, improve understanding of marine ecosystems, and help restore damaged areas, including coral reefs, wetlands, protected areas, and control invasive species. The 'Coral Reef Biodiversity' program headed by Bernard Salvat, University of Perpignan from 2002-2003, had 8 components covering the biophysical, cultural, social and economic context of coral reefs in the Indian Ocean, Australasia and Pacific islands on: knowledge of biodiversity; cultural Sponsoring Organisations, Coral Reef Programs & Monitoring Networks perceptions of biodiversity; genetic diversity of coral species; economic valuation of biodiversity; role of protected areas in maintaining coral reef biodiversity; coral bleaching; coral reef monitoring and natural recovery; and monitoring with emphasis on climate change. Contact: Gina Sardella-Sadiki, gina.sardella-sadiki@total.com; Aurélien Vadier, aurelien.vadier@total.com; 2, place de la Coupole – La Défense 6, 92078 Paris La Défense Cedex, France; www.total.com; holding.fondation@total.com

UNEP - UNITED NATIONS ENVIRONMENT PROGRAM

The mission of UNEP is to provide leadership and encourage partnerships in caring for the environment by inspiring, informing, and enabling nations and peoples to improve their quality of life without compromising that of future generations. UNEP makes a particular effort to nurture frameworks and initiatives at the local, national, regional and global level which enhance the participation of governments and civil society - the private sector, scientific community, NGOs and youth - in working together towards sustainable utilisation of natural resources. The challenge before UNEP is to implement an environmental agenda that is integrated strategically with the goals of economic development and social well-being; an agenda for sustainable development. Contact: UNEP, PO Box 30552, Nairobi, Kenya; cpinfo@unep.org; www.unep.org

UNEP - CORAL REEF UNIT (CRU)

The CRU is the focal point within UNEP and the UN system to guide and mobilize policies and actions to support the conservation and sustainable use of coral reefs to safeguard their biological and biodiversity functions, which provide goods and services for the benefit of people and the sustainable development of dependant communities. Co-located with other coral reef resources at UNEP-WCMC, the CRU works closely with UNEP divisions/programs and international partners such as the International Coral Reef Initiative (ICRI) and Operational Networks. CRU activities include: supporting international collaboration to reverse coral reef degradation; cooperating to promote the political understanding of the importance of coral reefs; reviewing and integrating information on international policies related to coral reefs; and promoting innovative partnerships to address new and emerging coral reef issues, such as cold-water coral reefs. Contact: Stefan Hain, UNEP Coral Reef Unit, 219 Huntingdon Road, Cambridge, CB3 0DL, UK; stefan.hain@unep-wcmc.org; www.corals.unep.org and www.coral.unep.ch

WWF – WORLDWIDE FUND FOR NATURE

WWF is the world's largest and most experienced independent conservation organisation, with more than 4.7 million members and a global network in 96 countries. The mission is to stop degradation of the world's natural environment. WWF leads efforts globally to safeguard marine ecosystems by: conserving cold water and tropical coral reefs; assisting coastal communities to manage MPAs effectively; and ending destructive fishing practices. There are activities in key regions throughout the tropics to establish networks of MPAs that safeguard the ecological integrity of larger reef systems. WWF has been instrumental in promoting innovative market incentives that reward responsible fishing methods. WWF also works to improve fisheries management, reduce bycatch fatalities of vulnerable species (such as whales and sea turtles), stop illegal trade in marine wildlife and reform government policies that undermine the ocean's web of life. Contact: Anita Van Breda, anita.vanbreda@wwfus.org; or Helen Fox, helen.fox@wwfus.org, WWF, 1250 Twenty-Fourth Street, NW, Washington, DC 20037; www.worldwildlife.org.

Appendix 2: Persons met/Institutions Visited

La Reunion

Mr. Jean Pascal Quod (ARVAM)
Mr. Lionel Bigot (ARVAM)
Mr. Bruce Cauvin (IOC RR National Focal Point)
Mr. Emmanuel Tessier (Director, Marine Park)
Mr. Lionel Gardes (Regional Direction Environment)
Mrs. Sandrine Gilson (Departement de La Reunion).

Rodrigues

Ms. Emily Hardman (Shoals Rodrigues)
Ms. Sabrina Desire (Shoals Rodrigues)
Mr. Franceau Aubret Grandcourt. (Commissioner for Environment, Housing, Infrastructure)
Mr. Chandrasen Matadeen (Department Head, Commission for Environment)

Comoros

Mr. Said Ahamada (AIDE)
Mr. Soifa Ahamed Solil (AIDE)
Mr. Mohamed Halifa (NFP ReCoMap)
Mr. Ismael Mohamed
Mr. Said Mohamed Ali Said (General secretary Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Environment.)
Mr. Farid Anasse (National Focal Point Convention)
Mr. Soalihy Hamadi (President of AIDE)
Mr. Salim Said (Association pour la protection de Gombessa)
Mr. Aboubacar Bounou Salim (Ministre de la Production Rurale et de 'l Environnement, Moheli)
Director of Fisheries, Moheli
Mr. Loutoufi Madi Abdallah (Focal Point ProGeCo Moheli)
Mr. Charraf –Eddine M'Sadie (National Director of Environment and Forestry).

Seychelles

Mr. Jude Bijoux (Seychelles National Coral Reef Network, employed by ReCoMap)
Mr. Wills Agricole (ReCoMap National Focal Point).
Mrs. Begum Nageon de l'Estang (Coordinator National Environment Action Plan)
Mr. Didier Dogley, Principal Secretary (Dept. of Environment)
Mr. Selby Remie, (Chair, Seychelles National Coral Reef Network and Vice Chairman East Africa Coral Reef Task Force)
Dr. Frauke Dogley (Chief Executive Officer, Seychelles Island Foundation).

Mr. Rony Renaud, Managing Director (Seychelles Center for Marine Research and Technology Marine Parks Authority)
Mr. Herve Barois, Coordinator (Island Conservation Society)
Mrs. Kersitin Henri, Project Coordinator (Nature Seychelles)
Mr. Flavien Joubert, Director (Department of Environment, Control of pollution)
Mr. Antoine Moustache, (Co-Chairman National Climate Change Committee).
Mr. Tim Kirkpatrick, Director of Programs (Global Vision International)
Mr. Steve Gwenin, Director of Programs (Global Vision International)
Ms. Britt Larsen, Regional Director (Global Vision International)
Mr. David Rowat (Marine Conservation Society)

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Ms. Patricia Davis, Community Centred Conservation.
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Mr. Aurilien Nhaboo, Reef Mauritius
Ms. Emilie Wiene, Reef Mauritius
Mr. Jean Michel Langlois, Mauritius Underwater Group.
Mr. Daniel Pelicier, Mauritius Underwater Group

Madagascar

Mr. Remy Ratsimbazafa, WorldWide Fund for Nature
Mr. Herilala Randriamahazo, Director, Marine and Coastal Program, Wildlife Conservation Society.
Mr. Jean Maharavo, National Focal Point RR, National Focal Point CRT, Centre Nationale de Recherche sur l'Environnement.

Kenya

Dr. Nyawira Muthiga, Wildlife Conservation Society and Chair of the Nairobi Convention Coral Reef Task Force (notes from telephone conversations between Jim Anderson and Dr Muthiga)

Tanzania

Dr. Chris Muhando, National Team Leader, GCRMN East Africa Node (Notes from conversation with Jim Anderson)